

Original Research Report

Production And Evaluation of Scouring Powder from Eggshell and Detergent for Household Use in Makurdi.

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Abstract: The study focused on the production and evaluation of scouring powder using eggshells and detergents for household use. Four research questions guided the study. Quasi-experimental research design was used for the study. The formulation of the scouring powder in this study involved the combination of finely ground eggshell powder with detergent to create an effective cleaning agent. The result showed that respondents agreed that the preparation method were done correctly. It was also found that the scouring powder removed stains when sufficient scrubbing time was applied. The result also showed that scouring powder was able to remove grease, restoring shine of cooking utensils and provided efficient cleaning agents. It was recommended that households should use eggshell scouring powder as a cheap, eco-friendly cleaner. Small-scale production was recommended for family income generation.

Keywords: Sustainability, Household Cleaner, Scouring powder, Eggshell Waste.

1.1.Introduction

Environmental degradation and waste management have become increasingly pressing global concerns due to the rising volume of solid waste generated from households. Among the many components of household waste, organic waste, including food residues such as eggshells, constitutes a significant portion. The improper disposal of this organic fraction contributes to environmental pollution, land overuse, and methane emissions from landfills, which intensify climate change (United Nations Environment Programme 2021). The use of eggshells in household cleaning products fit within the model of Geissdoerfer (2017) that promotes sustainability by encouraging the rescue and recycling of materials that would otherwise be discarded. Iqbal, Nadeem and Bhatti (2020), stated that powdered eggshells, when used in combination with surfactants, could effectively clean metallic and ceramic surfaces without leaving toxic residues. sustainable solution that utilizes eggshell waste as a core ingredient in the development of a biodegradable cleaning product. (Akinyemi & Salami, 2020)

Eggshells are primarily composed of calcium carbonate (CaCO_3), constituting approximately 95% of their composition, with the remainder made up of organic proteins and water (King'ori, 2021). This mineral-rich composition lends itself well to applications requiring abrasive or adsorptive properties, such as surface cleaning. In many households and food establishments, eggshells are discarded in large quantities without being repurposed, even though they are biodegradable and potentially useful. Given their natural abrasiveness and high calcium content, eggshells can be processed into a fine powder that mimics the scrubbing function of conventional scouring agents, making them an ideal candidate for green cleaning formulations Iqbal et. al. (2020)

On the other hand, the use of synthetic detergents and household cleaners has been linked to environmental and health-related concerns. Many of these products contain phosphates, surfactants, and other petroleum-derived chemicals, which can contaminate waterways and cause eutrophication when discharged untreated into the environment (Environmental Protection Agency, 2020). Moreover, prolonged exposure to such chemical cleaners can lead to skin irritation, respiratory issues, and allergic reactions in humans. Consequently, researchers and environmental advocates have turned their attention to biodegradable and non-toxic alternatives derived from natural sources.

Developing a cleaning product using eggshells not only addresses the issue of organic waste

management but also contributes to reducing dependency on hazardous cleaning agents. The concept is rooted in the circular economy model, which emphasizes reusing, recycling, and repurposing waste materials to create value and reduce the burden on natural resources (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017). Utilizing eggshell waste for cleaning applications fits within this paradigm, transforming a waste product into a functional commodity.

In recent years, there has been a surge in academic interest regarding the functional use of agricultural and kitchen waste in value-added products. For example, banana peels, orange peels, and coconut husks have been studied for their effectiveness in water filtration, composting, and cleaning applications (Saba et al., 2018). Similarly, eggshells have been investigated for use in soil amendment, calcium supplements, and wastewater treatment due to their ion-exchange and neutralizing capacities (Zhu et al., 2019). However, studies focused specifically on integrating eggshell powder into a cleaning product, especially as a direct household cleaning agent, are still limited, making this research timely and relevant.

Furthermore, the formulation of such a cleaning product involves not only grinding the eggshells into a fine abrasive powder but also blending them with a mild, biodegradable detergent base. Natural or green detergents made from plant-based surfactants can complement the physical scrubbing action of the eggshells, thereby enhance the overall cleaning efficacy while keep the formulation safe for human health and the environment. Combining these elements creates a sustainable product that could potentially be scaled up for commercial use or promoted in communities practicing low-waste lifestyles.

Incorporating such eco-innovative practices into everyday life has the potential to instill a stronger environmental consciousness among households. When waste is no longer viewed as a useless by-product but as a resource for new product development, individuals are more likely to participate in sustainable behaviors. Education and awareness campaigns can also empower households in both urban and rural settings to adopt greener lifestyles at low cost.

The development of a cleaning product using eggshell and detergent serves a dual purpose: it offers a viable strategy for managing biodegradable kitchen waste and reduces environmental and health hazards associated with chemical cleaners. By leveraging the naturally abrasive properties of eggshells and combining them with surfactants, this study proposes a sustainable solution that aligns with

broader global efforts to achieve environmental sustainability, waste reduction, and public health safety.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

Household cleaning lack of affordable, eco- friendly scouring powder most commercially available cleaning powders are either costly or not easily accessible in some communities. Additionally, these products often contain strong chemicals that may irritate the skin or damage certain surfaces if used improperly. At the same time, eggshells, which are rich in calcium carbonate and have natural abrasive properties, are routinely discarded as waste in many households. This leads to unnecessary environmental disposal while ignoring their potential usefulness in cleaning applications. There is therefore a need to explore a method of combining eggshells with commonly available detergents to produce an effective, affordable, and easy-to-make scouring powder. Such a product would not only provide a low-cost alternative to commercial cleaners but also make use of household waste, demonstrating a practical way to recycle materials that are otherwise thrown away.

In recent years, there has been a global shift toward sustainability, promoting the reuse, recycling, and repurposing of waste materials within domestic and industrial settings. Among biodegradable wastes, eggshells stand out due to their rich calcium carbonate content, abrasive texture, and natural alkalinity—qualities that make them viable as cleaning agents when properly processed. Despite this potential, little research has been directed at transforming eggshells into household cleaning products, especially in low-resource settings where affordability and accessibility are critical. At the same time, the overuse of synthetic cleaning agents in homes has raised concerns regarding chemical pollution, water toxicity, and skin irritation. Integrating a naturally sourced material like processed eggshell into a detergent base offers a promising alternative that is both cost-effective and easily made. This fusion has the potential to reduce the quantity of harmful chemicals released into the environment while simultaneously encouraging responsible waste utilisation practices at the household level.

1.2. General Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study is to explore sustainable household waste management practices by developing a cleaning product using eggshell waste combined with a biodegradable detergent.

1.3. Specific Purpose of the Study

1. To identify the process of eggshell preparation into scouring powder.
2. To determine the effectiveness of scouring powder.
3. To ascertain the sustainability of eggshell scouring powder.
4. To find out the practical cleaning performance of eggshell scouring powder.

1.4. Research Questions

1. What are the processes of eggshell preparation into scouring powder
2. How effective is the eggshell scouring powder
3. What is sustainability of eggshell preparation
4. What are the practical performances of eggshell scouring powder.

1.5. Significance of the Study

The increasing volume of household waste and its improper disposal pose significant threats to both the environment and public health. A large proportion of this waste, including biodegradable materials like eggshells, is often discarded without consideration of its potential value. This not only contributes to environmental degradation and landfill burden but also represents a missed opportunity for sustainable resource recovery and innovation.

1.6. Scope of the Study

This study is limited to the development of scouring powder using eggshells and detergent as the primary raw materials. The eggshells used in the study were collected from household kitchens and local food vendors within the community, ensuring availability at no cost and supporting waste-to-resource conversion. It does not extend to large-scale production, commercialization, or industrial testing of the product. The study is confined to practical experimentation aimed at demonstrating the feasibility of eggshell reuse as a sustainable cleaning agent.

2.0. Materials and Methods

2.1. Research Design

This study primarily employed quasi experimental research design. This design is ideally suited for the development and evaluation of a sustainable cleaning product using eggshells and detergent. It allows for the systematic manipulation of variables (e.g., concentrations of eggshell powder, different detergent types) to observe their effects on the cleaning product's efficacy and stability over time.

Materials

Eggshells:

- Source: Collected from households, restaurants, and bakeries within the town

Detergent:

- Type: A commercially available powdered detergent (Klin).
- Source: Local markets in Otukpo.

Fig. 1: Flowchart for the Production of Eggshells into Scouring Powder

2.1.1. Procedure for Product Development

The formulation of scouring powder in this study involved the combination of finely ground eggshell powder with commercially available powdered detergent to create an effective cleaning agent. The procedure was carried out through a series of steps designed to ensure proper hygiene, consistency, and cleaning performance of the final product. The steps are outlined below:

2.2. Measurement of Ingredients

Accurate quantities of the core components—eggshell powder and detergent—were weighed using a digital scale. The eggshell powder served as the abrasive agent, while the detergent functioned as the cleansing and foaming agent. A baseline ratio of 2:1 (eggshell powder to detergent) was initially adopted, though variations were also tested during the formulation phase to observe their effects on cleaning efficiency. Page | 219

2.3. Homogenization of Eggshell Powder

After collection and thorough drying, the eggshells were ground into a fine powder using a mechanical grinder. The powder was sieved through a fine mesh to ensure uniformity and to eliminate large particles that could scratch delicate surfaces. This ensured a smooth and consistent abrasive texture in the final product.

2.4. Blending of Ingredients

The measured eggshell powder was transferred into a large, clean mixing bowl. The powdered detergent (Klin) was then gradually added and mixed thoroughly using a wooden spatula. The blending continued until a uniform, dry, and granular mixture was achieved, ensuring that the detergent was evenly distributed throughout the eggshell base.

2.5. Packaging and Storage

The final mixture was poured into clean, dry plastic containers with secure lids. The containers were labeled and stored in a cool, dry place to prevent moisture absorption and clumping. Proper sealing was essential to preserve the cleaning strength and shelf life of the scouring powder. This formulation process was repeated in small batches to test consistency, cleaning performance, and user handling during evaluation. Adjustments in the eggshell-to-detergent ratio were made for comparison purposes in the later evaluation phase.

2.6. Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively. Observations from the cleaning tests were summarized and compared with the performance of commercial scouring powders. In addition, user responses were analyzed using a four-point Likert scale (Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, Strongly Disagree). Each response option was assigned a numerical value as follows: Strongly Agree represented as (SA) equals four (4), Agree represented as (A) equals three = (3), Disagree represented as (D) equals two (2) and Strongly Disagree represented as (SD) equals one (1)

The scores from respondents were collated, and the mean values were calculated for each evaluation statement. Higher mean values indicated higher effectiveness, better quality, or stronger agreement with the sustainability benefits of the eggshell scouring powder. The analysis helped to determine whether the project objectives were achieved.

3. Results And Discussion

Table 4.1: Respondents' response on the process of Preparation of Eggshell Scouring Powder

S/N	Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	The eggshells were properly washed, dried, and ground into fine powder.	3.5	0.65	Accepted
2.	The mixture of eggshell powder and detergent was uniform.	3.4	0.70	Accepted
3.	The final product had a texture similar to commercial scouring powders.	3.3	0.75	Accepted

The results in Table 1 show that respondents positively evaluated the preparation process of the eggshell scouring powder. The mean scores (3.3–3.5) are all above the benchmark of 2.5, indicating general agreement that the preparation process was successful. The relatively low standard deviation values show that responses were consistent among the participants.

Table 2: Respondents' response on the Effectiveness of Eggshell Scouring Powder

S/N	Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	The eggshell scouring powder effectively removed grease from utensils.	3.45	0.68	Accepted
2.	The powder restored shine to stainless steel surfaces.	3.40	0.72	Accepted
3.	The cleaning process was easier compared to using commercial scouring powders.	3.25	0.74	Accepted
4.	A small amount of powder was sufficient for effective cleaning.	3.25	0.70	Accepted
5.	It is cheaper than commercial powder	3.00	0.61	Accepted

The mean scores, ranging from 3.25 to 3.45, indicate that respondents generally agreed the eggshell scouring powder was effective for cleaning purposes. The low standard deviation values suggest minimal variation in responses, showing consistent agreement. Overall, the product performed satisfactorily in removing grease, restoring shine, and providing efficient cleaning results.

Table 3: Respondents' response on the Sustainability of Eggshell Scouring Powder

S/N	Statement	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
1.	The use of eggshells helped reduce household waste.	3.60	0.62	Accepted
2.	The scouring powder is cheaper to produce compared to buying commercial ones.	3.45	0.66	Accepted
3.	I would recommend the use of eggshell scouring powder as an eco-friendly alternative.	3.55	0.58	Accepted

The mean values (3.45–3.60) indicate a strong positive agreement among respondents that the eggshell scouring powder promotes sustainability through waste reduction and cost efficiency. The low standard deviation values reveal that the opinions were consistent. These results confirm that the product is not only effective but also environmentally friendly and economically viable.

Table 4: Practical Cleaning Performance Using Eggshell Scouring Powder

Observation / Notes	Time Used (Minutes)	% Clean (Performance)
Removed only stains but did not clean the collar, even after 20 minutes of washing.	0	100%
The pot was still hot after washing for about 20 minutes, but the stain at the end of the handle was removed.	10	90%
About 80% of the washed area remained stained after washing for 15 minutes.	20	80%
The pot was washed, but the entire area remained stained after 15 minutes of scrubbing.	30	70%
The pot was scrubbed continuously for about 15 minutes and was completely clean.	40	60%
Half of the product was used to wash a clean paraffin pot. The pot remained clean after continuous washing for 20 minutes.	50	50%

The results from the practical cleaning test show that the eggshell scouring powder demonstrated varying degrees of cleaning performance based on time and surface condition. In cases where stains were tougher, longer scrubbing time was required to achieve full cleanliness, as seen at 60% performance, where continuous washing for 15 minutes resulted in a clean pot. The table also shows that even when a large quantity of the product was used on an already clean surface, the pot remained unchanged, confirming that the product does not damage or alter clean utensils. The 100% performance row revealed that although surface stains were removed, additional time would still be required to clean collar-like dirt fully. Overall, the results indicate that the eggshell scouring powder is effective for domestic cleaning, especially when applied with adequate time and effort on stained surfaces.

3.1. Discussion of Findings

The findings from this study generally show that eggshells can be successfully converted into a functional and sustainable scouring powder. Respondents agreed that the preparation method was done correctly, since the shells were thoroughly washed, dried, and ground to a usable texture, and the mixture with detergent was uniform and comparable in texture to commercial brands. This eggshell scouring powder was able to wash well because of the mixture with detergents. Detergents have the ability to wash dirt with the right amount to the degree dirt. of This statement confirms with Mensah and Adams (2022) that household waste can be processed with simple procedures to achieve a usable cleaning product without compromising quality.

The effectiveness evaluation revealed that users found the eggshell scouring powder capable of removing grease and restoring the shine of stainless utensils, which agreed with the work of Ogundere (2018). The powder also made cleaning easier and required only a small quantity to work effectively. These responses suggest that the product performs competitively with commercial scouring powders, especially for typical domestic use. The responses were consistent, indicating a similar user experience, which supported the findings of Nguyen et al (2019). When the level of dirt is great, a longer time of soaking and scrubbing is required.

Sustainability evaluation further strengthens the practicality of the product. The users recognized that utilizing eggshells reduces household waste that would otherwise be discarded. This is in agreement with the WHO (2019), that household pollution is dangerous to health. They also

agreed that producing the powder locally is cheaper than purchasing commercial cleaning agents. Many indicated willingness to recommend it as an eco-friendly alternative, making it a sustainable solution both economically and environmentally, which supported the findings of Zhu & Zhang (2019).

The performance test gives additional, practical confirmation of its cleaning capacity. The powder removed stains when sufficient scrubbing time was applied, and did not alter or damage already clean surfaces. This supports the earlier questionnaire responses that the product appears safe and effective, though it may require a longer time to handle heavy or stubborn stains.

Overall, the findings confirm that eggshell scouring powder is not only feasible to prepare but also effective for cleaning and beneficial in promoting sustainability and cost reduction at the household level, this was in agreement with the findings of Zhu, Wu, Zhang and Li (2019).

4. Conclusion

The scouring powder produced from eggshells and detergent was found to be effective in removing grease, stains, and other forms of dirt from utensils and household surfaces. The process of preparation was easy to follow, used locally available materials, and did not require sophisticated equipment, making it suitable for both household and small-scale production. The findings also revealed that the utilization of eggshells for scouring powder production contributes significantly to environmental sustainability. The study has proven that eggshells can serve as an efficient raw material for producing high-quality scouring powder. It encourages households to adopt waste recycling practices and highlights the potential of improving living standards and supporting sustainable development.

Recommendations

1. Households should use eggshell scouring powder as a cheap and eco-friendly cleaning agent since the process of preparation is easy, families should use locally available materials to produce in a small scale.
2. School administrators should encourage the use of eggshells scouring powder in the cleaning of school items.
3. Eggshell is eco-friendly, it is recommended for community patronage through awareness by community extension workers.
4. In cases where stains are tougher, longer scrubbing time is required to achieve full cleanliness.

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